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22. Research in Higher Education

Panel Discussion

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Well-being in Academia During the Pandemic

Gökçe Gökalp¹, Inge van der Weijden², Annelien Mortier³, Neda Bebiroglu⁴, Gabor Kismihok⁵, Mete Kurtoglu¹

¹Middle East Technical University; ²University of Leiden, The Netherlands; ³Ghent University, ECOOM, Belgium; ⁴Observatoire de la Recherche et des Carrières Scientifiques-FNRS, Belgium; ⁵Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology (TIB), Germany

Presenting Author: Gökalp, Gökçe; van der Weijden, Inge; Mortier, Annelien; Bebiroglu, Neda

In the past decade, institutions such as the World Health Organisation (WHO), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the European Commission (EC) have increasingly endorsed governments and organizations to include mental health among their top priorities. Compared to industry, the academic sector is lagging behind, both in terms of practical and scientific evidence on well-being and mental health within academia and research. According to a comparison of different occupational groups, academics rank among those with the highest levels of common mental problems: the prevalence of common psychological disorders estimated to be between 32% and 42% among academic employees and postgraduate students, compared to approximately 19% in the general population (Levecque, K. et al., 2017).

A recent report by OECD (2021) on research precariat highlighted the worsening working conditions of postdoctoral researchers and their detrimental effects on researcher's well-being and encouraged stakeholders to quickly implement actions to prevent a loss of research talent. In addition to this picture COVID-19 has significant effects on the working conditions in academia related to research, teaching and learning activities, worsening the pre-existing problem. There is a growing literature on how researchers, in general, and early career researchers (ECR) in particular, are affected by the pandemic in terms of their research activity and environments, (academic) career development and prospects, and mental health and well-being. There are some reports pointing an increase in job-loss fears, interrupted research and anxiety about the future (Woolston, 2020a) and seeking exit plans for leaving academia due to conditions caused by the pandemic (Woolston, 2020b). Although many negative consequences were identified due to lockdowns and other pandemic restrictions, there is also some evidence of promising learning and new ways of doing things, such as improved opportunities to attend virtual conferences. These changes can also result in beneficial effects on ECR's mental health and well-being.

Based on recent studies and insights from Belgium, The Netherlands and Turkey, this panel discussion aims to focus on the impact of the pandemic on working in academia specifically under following themes:

- Mental health and well-being of PhD candidates and ECRs.
- Relationship between risk factors associated with Covid-19, and the well-being of PhD candidates and ECRs.
- Support mechanisms at the national/institutional levels
- Job transition of doctorate holders
- Positive consequences of Covid on researchers

Participants of this panel discussion are members of the COST Action CA19117: "Researcher Mental Health" (ReMO) which focuses on well-being and mental health within academia, a theme of strategic importance for the European Research Area. By working at the European, national, institutional and individual levels ReMO network aims to create institutional environments that foster mental health and well-being, reduce mental health stigma, and empower researchers when it comes to well-being at work.

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Chair
Gábor Kismihók, TIB, Germany
Gabor.Kismihok@tib.eu